

their restoration and inheritance patterns during 1992-93 rabi season (Sep-Jan). All were found to be effective restorers and inherited digenically.

To determine the relationship among the genes, these five testers were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals. The F₁ generation of 10 R × R combinations was raised along with cytoplasmic male sterile line V20 A; A × (R × R) crosses were made. These

10 test cross F₁ progenies (A × (R × R)) were raised at 20- × 19-cm spacing during 1993 kharif season (Jun-Sep). Each combination had 10 rows with 20 plants per row. Their pollen and spikelet fertilities were scored (see table).

The restorer lines differed in their gene action. The test cross progenies from T₁ × T₃, T₁ × T₅, T₃ × T₅, and T₂ × T₄ did not yield any sterile progeny. These lines have identical R alleles

between them while remaining crosses showed segregation, indicating the alleles differed among their parents. These results suggest that the five restorer lines can be divided into group 1 = T₁, T₃, and T₅ and group 2 = T₂ and T₄, which possess different pairs of R genes. A suitable combination of any two of the pairs seems to restore fertility in male sterile lines. ■

Breeding methods

Identifying restorers and maintainers for five cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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Two new cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, Pusa 3 A and Pusa 5 A, were developed. Pusa 3 A has in its background high-yielding Basmati variety Pusa Basmati 1. Pusa 5 A has the aromatic, non-Basmati line Pusa 150. These lines, along with IR58025A, PMS2 A, and PMS3 A, which possess CMS wild abortive cytoplasm, were used to make test crosses. During the 1994 wet season, 326 hybrids and their respective parents were evaluated to identify effective restorers and maintainers for the CMS lines. Each genotype was transplanted in 3-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Standard agronomic practices were followed.

Five plants from each genotype were randomly selected and used for analyzing pollen and spikelet fertility. Anthers from upper, middle, and lower portions

Restorers and maintainers for five CMS lines. New Delhi, India. 1994.

CMS line	Restorers (no.)	Restorers	Maintainers (no.)	Maintainers
IR58025 A	36	PRR3, PRR5, PRR7, PRR8, PRR11, PRR12, PRR16, PRR22, PRR23, PRR25, PRR34, PRR35, PRR38, PRR42, PRR43, PRR44, PRR74, PRR79, PRR82, PRR98, PRR99, PRR100, PRR101, PRR102, PRR103, PRR104, PRR105, PRR107, PRR112, PRR113, PRR114, PRR115, PRR116, PRR117, PRR118, PRR119	7	TC7-2-1-92-39, TC11-3, TC23, TC25-41, P615-K-61, P615-K-271, P615-4-1
PMS3 A	13	PRR2, PRR8, PRR10, PRR24, PRR33, PRR45, PRR47, PRR55, PRR83, PRR84, PRR85, PRR87, PRR89	4	P615-K-160, RCPL 1-87-4, PP94-429, PP94-432
PMS2 A	4	PRR3, PRR5, PRR44, PRR85	3	ADT2008-2-7-1, P1191-3, P1192-2
Pusa 3 A	6	PRR69 ^a , PRR70 ^a , PRR71 ^a , PRR90, PRR94, PRR95	5	TC4-721, TC7-3-1, TCII-7-3-4-1, TC120, HKR91-410
Pusa 5 A	2	PRR57, PRR91	2	P615-K-61, P615-K-172
Total	61		21	

^a = Basmati restorers.

of half emerged panicles were collected and squashed in 2.2% I-KI stain to observe pollen fertility. Cultivars with up to 1% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as perfect maintainers, those with 60-100% pollen and 80-100% spikelet fertility as potential restorers, and the rest as partial restorers.

Three potential Basmati restorers were identified for Pusa 3 A. The frequency of restorers (19%) was higher than that of maintainers (6%) (see table).

We are using the potential restorers to develop new hybrids with improved quality characteristics. Some perfect maintainers with good agronomic traits are being converted into new CMS lines. ■

Androgenesis in rice breeding

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Plant regeneration efficiency from anther culture of F₁ cross Pankaj × *O. rufipogon* has been improved using He2 + NAA + Kin 0.5 + ABA 2 mg/liter + 5% maltose as

the callus induction medium (see table). Our objective was to transfer the submergence tolerance from the wild species *O. rufipogon* Griff. to the *O. sativa* variety Pankaj.

We used modified MS (NAA 0.5 + Kin 2 mg/liter + 3% sucrose) medium for plant regeneration. Several chlorophyll-deficient plants (albino, xantha, viridis, albo-viridis, virido-albina, virido-xantha,

and striata) and green plants that have different ploidy numbers were obtained. Among the regenerated plants, 73.3% were double haploids. These lines were grown in the field, where 74.8% survived. We examined 696 androgenic lines for different qualitative and quantitative characters. Statistical analysis revealed that the characters within one line were relatively uniform and stably heritable. Among